

Analyzing Academic Social Networks with Machine Learning Approaches

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ABSTRACT Academic social networks are a concept developed specifically in the context of academic big data, which refers to the complex academic network established by academic institutions and their connections. To study the rich structural kinds and related information about academic social networks, there are a variety of scholarly big data processing approaches. Nowadays, we can quickly get a variety of academic data, making it simpler to examine and investigate academic social networks. Therefore, it is important to study machine learning techniques in academic social network analysis, focus on practical implementations, and open avenues for further research. In this paper We explored the theoretical components of academic social network analysis using machine learning-technique, as well as the representation, tools, and techniques utilized for analysis, in this research. The source of data as well as its uses are also discussed in this study.

INDEX TERMS academic social networks, Social Networks, Machine learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this context, the field of academic social network study has evolved. The Social Network Analysis (SNA) is based on the concept that the value of relationships between interaction units is a key factor in evaluating and analyzing social interactions.[1] The social network technique has been increasingly significant in the computer information revolution in recent years ("The number of published applications has grown at roughly 250 percent each year over the previous five years"—Wasserman and Faust, 1994a). The identification of the most important, prominent, or central individuals; the identification of hubs and authorities; and the finding of communities are some of the frequent tasks of social network analysis. [2] These activities are particularly beneficial in the process of extracting knowledge from networks and, as a result, in the problem-solving process. Social network analysis is becoming a prominent method in a variety of domains, from statistics to machine learning, due to the engaging character of such challenges and the great potential offered by such studies. Machine learning refers to the evolution of systems that execute artificial intelligence tasks. Neural networks, fuzzy theory, genetic algorithms, and support vector machines are examples of machine learning components. Mitchell is a good place to start if you want to learn more about machine learning (1997).[3] Academic Social Networks (ASNs) are huge, heterogeneous networks made up of many different entities (publications, academics, etc.) and their connections (citations, coauthorships, etc.). (Wu et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2008). Scholars have worked on a diverse range of academic areas and data mining projects. Here are a few illustrations: (Amjad et al., 2015, 2017), author interests discovery (Daud, 2012), rising star Finding (Daud et al., 2013, 2015), academic recommendations (Guns and Rousseau, 2014), and community detection (Khan et al., 2017a) are all examples of community detection.[4]

As a result of the increased interest in ASNs, numerous ASN sites now provide SBD gathering and analysis. Microsoft Academic and Google Scholar, for example, offer document searching, whereas Cite u Like concentrates on citation relationship management. [5]. Academic Social Networks are developed via academic activities and knowledge (ASNs). This expression may investigate ASNs at a variety of spatial and temporal dimensions to describe patterns in new scientific disciplines and advance science's potential.[6] ASNs can be formed in a variety of methods, with co-authors being the most formal kind of academic activity (Fu et al., 2014). We can disclose the decisions and trade-offs of researchers in their careers by analyzing citation networks, and this is also one of SciSci's research interests.[7] There are now several search engines and digital libraries that make their datasets available to scholars investigating ASNs. Academic datasets are compiled from academic texts that contain a variety of different forms of data. Many of them, such as A Miner, American Physical Society (APS), DBLP, Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG), Open Academic Graph, and Open Research Corpus, are free to download. Academic social networks can take on a variety of topological forms. Scholars' academic social conduct may alter over time. Nodes in static networks never crash, and edges remain functioning. [8] Static networks, according to researchers, can lead to a persistent high degree of collaboration (Rand et al., 2014). The structure of a network becomes increasingly complicated as the scale of networked data grows. As a result, both the computation time and the complexity of the problem rise at the same time. As a result, Benson et al. (2016) created a generalized framework of higher-order connection patterns using a graph based on subnetworks. Real-world networks are, for the most part, dynamic. Nodes or edges may arrive or vanish in dynamic networks, causing the topology to vary over time. Because they can explain both compositions and interactions, dynamic networks are widely employed (Rand et al., 2011).

The use of SNs as a tool of analysis is a cost-effective way to examine SBD. Researchers develop links in academic networks through a range of academic activities (Fu et al., 2014). [9] Currently, there is a study being done on various types of communication among people. SBD's many entities have piqued people's curiosity. Of academics (Luo and Hsu, 2009). Furthermore, technological advancements and breakthroughs in data analysis, as well as recent advancements in the display of SNs The use of software makes it easier to investigate these connections. in addition to a dynamic display (Luo and Hsu, 2009). Science of Science (SciSci) describes science as a complex, interconnected system. Social Networks (SNs) are groups of people or organizations that are linked together in a specific setting, such as collaboration or socializing. [10] Nodes and edges are employed in SNs to represent entities and their interactions, respectively, to aid in data analysis and mining. The examination of SNs can reveal the network relationships generated during the spread of information. The use of SNs as a tool of analysis is a cost-effective way to examine SBD.

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The rest of the **paper is organized** as follows: Section II explores the related works, Section III Methodology, Section IV Conclusion...

2. RELATED WORK

Social networks have been measured on various datasets including online social networks (Lusseau et al., 2003) to those with adult content (Academic and Glance, 2005).

They used methods of learning from bigger networks. Social data mining is used to improve bio-inspired intelligent systems with swarm optimization, ant colony, and cultural algorithms are discussed in Choa et al. (2008). Machine Learning [12] is based on the premise that computers can learn from data, detect patterns, and make conclusions with minimal human intervention. Machine Learning algorithms can change over time. Machine learning's iterative component exposes models to fresh data, allowing them to change. They use past computations to make dependable, repeatable judgments and outcomes. This improves the system's efficiency and makes it more stable.

Originally researched in the social sciences on relatively modest sizes to allow for the computer, data storage, and data gathering capabilities of the time, academic social network analysis has been an active topic of study for some years. How individuals in the actual world constructed their social and commercial networks, how influence could be simulated, and how scant and difficult-to-come-by data might support diverse scientific ideas about social systems were the primary scientific topics. [13] The discovery of the "small world" phenomenon and its formal analysis are examples of early analytic work. Manual processing requires too much time and effort because of the enormous amount of SBD and varied types of ASNs. Using network characteristics, we may generate, analyze, and display ASNs using analytic tools. The following are the functions of ASN's analysis tools etwork characterization, relational mining, community recognition, and visualization are just a few examples of how flexible it is.

There are several tools available now, such as CiteSpace (Chen, 2004), CitNet- Explorer (Van Eck and Waltman, 2014), Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009), HistCite (Garfield and Pudovkin, 2004), iGraph (Csardi and Nepusz, 2006), NetworkX (Hagberg et al., 2008), NodeXL (Smith et al., 2009), Pajek (Batagelj (Van Eck and Waltman, 2011). We'll give you a quick rundown of the facts regarding these tools below.

Machine Learning is based on the premise that computers can learn from data, detect patterns, and make conclusions with minimal human intervention. [14] Machine Learning algorithms can change over time. Machine learning's iterative component exposes models to fresh data, allowing them to change. They use past computations to make dependable, repeatable judgments and outcomes. This improves the system's efficiency and makes it more stable.

The academic social network analysis may be defined as a set of approaches for obtaining knowledge about human interactions from the ties they form usually as members of various social networks. These networks might include family, friends, firms or organizations where they work, or social media sites where they engage. In more technical terms, a social network is made up of a finite number of actors and the relationships between them. [15]

This research looks at how academics utilize a specific type of social media called social networking sites. Social networking sites, according to Boyd and Ellison (2008), are web-based services that allow users to create a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and view and traverse their list of connections as well as those made by others within the system. [16] According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), social networking sites "allow users to interact by creating personal information profiles, asking friends and colleagues to have access to those profiles, and sending messages to those profiles."

Title on papers	Year	Authors	Focusing points	Conference/Journal Name
Collaboration Recommendation on Academic Social Networks.	2010	Giseli Rabello Lopes ¹ , Mirella M. Moro ²	This paper presents an innovative approach to academic Social Networks. Specifically, introduce the architecture for such an approach and the metrics involved in recommending collaborations.	Conference paper
Combining Machine Learning and Social Network Analysis to Reveal the Organizational Structures	2019	Mateusz Nurek and Radosław Michalski	The key concept of this work is to evaluate how well social network analysis and combined with other features of organizational social network. Also, compare how traditional methods of machine learning classification.	Springer
Academic Social Network extraction Researchers	2007	Jie Tang, Duo Zhang, and Limin Yao	This paper addresses the issue of extraction of an academic researcher's social network. By researching social network extraction, we are aimed at finding, extracting, and fusing the 'semantic'	IEEE
A Survey on Machine Learning Methodologies in Social Network Analysis	2020	Runa Ganguli, Akash Mehta, Soumya Sen.	This paper surveys the existing work on a fake profile detection personality trait recognition of depression detection based on using machine learning algorithms in social network analysis and presents a comparative study of the different approaches.	Conference paper
Parallel Computing for Machine Learning in Social Network Analysis	2017	George Cybenko	This paper discusses the state of each ingredient with a specific focus on, how deep learning can apply to large-scale social network analysis and also the computing resources required to make such analyses feasible.	IEEE
Machine Learning for Social Network Analysis: A Systematic Literature Review	2017	Sagar S. De, Gi-Nam Wang	This paper focuses on reviewed and the theoretical aspects of social network analysis with a combination of machine learning-based techniques, its representation, tools and techniques used for analysis.	Conference paper
Analyzing Academic Social Networks with Machine Learning Approaches	2024	Mohamed Muaawiye Hilowle	In this paper, we explored the theoretical components of academic social network analysis using machine learning-technique, as well as the representation, tools, and techniques utilized for analysis, in this research.	Article paper

Table 1 Comparison of papers on Academic Social Network Analysis using Machine Learning technique

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Academic Social Networks

In recent years, social network analysis has been a prominent approach in a variety of domains, including social media networks, transportation networks (e.g., track control), epidemiology networks (e.g., epidemic spread models), and online networks (e.g., building the structure of the World Wide Web). It is utilized not just to monitor online social media apps like Twitter and Facebook, but also to deliver integrated scientific research services. [17] Social Networks (SNs) are groups of people or organizations who are linked together in a certain setting, such as collaboration or socializing.

The use of SNs as a tool of analysis is a cost-effective way to examine SBD. Researchers develop links in academic networks through a range of academic activities (Fu et al., 2014). Researchers are currently very interested in researching different patterns of communication among various elements of SBD (Luo and Hsu, 2009). Furthermore, technical breakthroughs in data analysis, as well as recent innovations in SN visualization tools, make it easier to explore and exhibit these associations dynamically (Luo and Hsu, 2009).

3.2 Academic Social Networks in Scholarly Data

Science is defined as a complex, self-organizing, and developing network of academic knowledge by the Science of Science (SciSci) (Fortunato et al., 2018). Academic Social Networks are social networks developed via academic activities and information in SBD (ASNs). This expression may investigate ASNs at a variety of spatial and temporal dimensions to describe patterns in new scientific disciplines and advance science's potential. [18] ASNs can be formed in a variety of methods, with co-authors being the most formal kind of academic activity (Fu et al., 2014).

We can disclose the decisions and trade-offs of researchers in their careers by researching citation networks, which is also one of SciSci's research interests. Furthermore, several studies have indicated that well-connected academic social networks are more prolific (Lopes et al., 2011), making them essential to research for us.

There are currently many surveys that use SNs in a variety of fields, such as Anomaly Detection (Kaur and Singh, 2016), Signed Network Mining in Social Media (Tang et al., 2016), [19] Mobile Social Networks (Hu et al., 2015), Vehicular Social Networks (Rahim et al., 2017), and Social Influence in Social Networks (Peng et al., 2018), but no overview of SN. Meanwhile, there have been some developments. analyzed current scholarly data research trends and highlighted development obstacles. Future research has been plotted out using academic data platforms. directions for different periods of the big data life cycle.

4. Academic Social Network Analysis Tools

Manual processing requires too much time and effort because of the enormous amount of SBD and varied types of ASNs. Using network characteristics, we may generate, analyze, and display ASNs using analytic tools. The following are the functions of ASN's analysis tools:

Network characterization, relational mining, community recognition, and visualization are just a few examples of how flexible it is. [20] There are several tools available now, such as CiteSpace (Chen, 2004), CitNet- Explorer (Van Eck and Waltman, 2014), Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009), HistCite (Garfield and Pudovkin, 2004), iGraph (Csardi and Nepusz, 2006), NetworkX (Hagberg et al., 2008), NodeXL (Smith et al., 2009), Pajek (Batagelj (Van Eck and Waltman, 2011).

4.1 Key Mining Technologies

Academic social network analysis includes a sub-task called academic social network mining. Its goal is to uncover academic social connections, which may be defined as the link between two or more things. With the advent of both available data and emerging technology, recent developments have concentrated on mining interrelationships. We divide ASN mining measures into four groups based on data mining and SN mining perspectives:

- x Similarity measure.
- x Statistical Relational Learning.
- x Graphic mining.

- x Machine learning.

These approaches are often used to extract relationships in social networks and, depending on the network aliation, might be used in academic social networks. They may be used in community discovery, relation mining, and link prediction, to name a few applications. The primary categories and uses of these approaches in academic social networks [21].

4.1.1 Similarity Measures

Similarity metrics are used to determine how similar entities in a network are. There are two types of problems with existing similarity models in multi-relational social networks: Algorithms that are content-based, as well as linkage-based and structural algorithms.

4.1.2 Linkage-based and Structural Methods

The majority of existing network mining research is focused on traditional algorithms like PageRank (Page et al., 1999) and SimRank (Jeh and Widom, 2002), which rank data using random walk approaches. The goal of the random walk method is to calculate the likelihood of passing each node. [21] As a result, in networks, a well-connected structure will have a higher PageRank score. These algorithms and their applications are widely used in ASNs for collaboration pattern mining and recommendation (Strohman et al., 2007; Lu and Zhou, 2011; Li et al., 2014), rising star identification (Daud et al., 2013; Li et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2016), and scientific evaluation (Chen et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2013b).

4.1.3 Content-based Methods

Distance-based algorithms, cosine-based algorithms, correlation-based algorithms, and the Jaccard coefficient are the most well-known approaches for content-based analysis. Murkowski distance, Chebyshev distance, Manhattan distance, and Euclidean distance are all popular methods for calculating distance similarities and grouping things with similar properties. These approaches have been popular as a means to use information about an item to generate recommendations in scholarly recommendation and analysis (Ding et al., 2014).

4.1.4 Statistical Relational Learning

Travers and Milgram (1977) set the groundwork for a thorough investigation of structural characteristics in large-scale networks. Statistical features appear in many typical social networks in different ways. We may explore the analysis of connection behavior among nodes and how the structure evolves with the evolution of the network by investigating the properties of these networks on a broad scale. Theoretical statistics and data representation are combined in statistical relational learning. It focuses on the data's combined probability distribution. [22] At this point, most statistical relational learning research focuses on the difficulties of learning probabilistic models from relational data. Researchers have suggested three properties to develop models for statistical relational learning, including concentrated linkage, degree disparity, and relational

autocorrelation. Significant discrepancies in connectedness among different sorts of objects can be represented by concentrated lineage. The different degrees of different sorts of things cause degree discrepancy. The relevant value of the same characteristic under different aliases is known as relational autocorrelation.

4.1.5 Graph Mining

Graph mining, which is an important part of network mining, has recently gained popularity. It refers to the process of extracting meaningful knowledge and information from large amounts of data utilizing graph models. It may be used in ASNs for a variety of tasks, including link analysis, group discovery, and metadata mining. In the field of graph mining, frequent sub-graph mining is a hot issue. Apriority-based algorithms (e.g., AGM (Abramowitz et al., 1966), ACGM, pathjoin (Li et al., 2001), etc.) and FP-growth algorithms (e.g., gSpan (Yan and Han, 2002), Close Graph (Yan and Han, 2003), FFSM (Huan et al., 2003), etc.) are examples of related approaches. [23] They increasingly broaden their scope. to obtain frequent subgraphs with slightly different edge extensions Wang et al. (2005) also presented the Graph Miner method, which is an index-based frequent subgraph mining approach for mining frequent patterns from huge disk-based graph datasets. Borgwardt et al. (2006) proposed Dynamic GREW for existent pattern mining on static graphs for time series graphs for dynamic graph mining. Significant subgraph mining (Sugiyama et al., 2015) and dense subgraph mining are two further graph mining techniques (Gunnemann et al., 2010). These methods are commonly used to extract and evaluate interactions between entities in ASNs, such as community mining, scientific pattern uncovering (He et al. 2012), and impact prediction (Pobiedina and Ichise, 2014).

4.1.6 Machine Learning

Supervised procedures and unsupervised measures are two of the most important responsibilities in machine learning approaches to academic social network mining. The relation task in the supervised domain seeks to extract a collection of known relations based on mentions of an entity pair. Learning needs a huge quantity of training data. Unsupervised tasks, on the other hand, are concerned with guessing which connection class a given item belongs to beyond the labels provided. [24] Deep learning is a subfield of machine learning that is also very essential. As a result, we divide the major mining approaches into three groups: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and deep learning.

4.1.6.1 Supervised Learning

Feature-based and kernel-based approaches are the two types of traditional supervised learning methods. Mining jobs in ASNs are often classified as a classification challenge, according to related theories. For supervised learning, there are too many categorization models, such as Decision Trees, Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, and K-Nearest Neighbors. Relational categorization may also be done with regression models (Herlocker et al., 1999). These approaches' performance is determined by feature selection and parameter choices. For

example, Akritidis and Bozani (2013) used machine learning techniques to tackle the challenge of automated paper classification. Many of the taxonomy's labels were related to authors, co-authors, keywords, and published publications. XGboost (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) is a recently suggested machine learning model. In certain ways, it outperforms support vector machines and neural networks in terms of prediction.

Its drawback is that it necessitates a large number of modification factors.[25]

To anticipate the influence of institutions, Bai et al. (2017b) employed the XGboost model to synthesize the characteristics of individual ability, institutional location, and national GDP.

4.6.1.2 Unsupervised Learning

In practice, supervised learning generally necessitates precise labels, which require a significant amount of time and effort to develop datasets. Unsupervised learning is defined as learning without labeling a dataset, and it is sometimes referred to as a clustering challenge in relation extraction. To detect related things, several strategies have been developed. Currently, there are five main clustering algorithms: hierarchical techniques, partition-based methods, density-based methods, grid-based methods, and model-based approaches, with hierarchical methods and partition-based methods being the most often employed (Han et al., 2011). Partition-based algorithms partition a dataset into k pieces by optimizing the evaluation function, which necessitates researchers deciding on the value of k as an input. Kmeans, K-medoids (Park and Jun 2009), and CLARANS (Ng and Han, 2002) are examples of partition-based algorithms.[26] Different layers of segmentation clustering are used in hierarchical approaches, and the segmentation between levels has a layered connection. One of the obvious advantages of Partition based approaches is that it does not require input parameters. Researchers must, however, indicate the end condition. BIRCH (Zhang et al., 1996), DBSCAN (Birant and Kut, 2007), and CURE are examples of hierarchical algorithms (Guha et al., 1998).

Although unsupervised learning is less effective than supervised learning, it can aid in classification by splitting samples into several categories that can be labeled by manual annotation and selecting representative examples from a large dataset for classifier training.

5. Deep Learning

Deep learning is one of the most significant data representation-based machine learning approaches. It includes both supervised and unsupervised learning, just as machine learning approaches. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are a common supervised learning approach (Krizhevsky et al., 2012). Deep learning without supervision may be classified into two types. One is based on the autoencoder (Rifai et al., 2011), whose major purpose is to reconstruct the original data in one piece from the abstract data. Others are built around Boltzmann machines (Aarts and Korst, 1988). When the machine reaches a steady state, the major purpose of these algorithms is to recreate the original data.[27]

6. Academic Social Network Sites

A plethora of ASN sites have sprung up to assist researchers in creating personal profiles that allow them to discuss interests and articles. We take a look at a few of the most popular websites. In 2006, AMiner was created using Perl CGI programming. There are currently almost 130 million researchers, 233 million papers, and 754 million citations on this platform (Tang et al., 2008). AMiner's current responsibilities include: (1) creating semantic-based researcher profiles; (2) integrating SBD from many sources; (3) building heterogeneous networks, and (4) analyzing intriguing trends. A great number of ASNs research, such as extraction (Tang et al., 2010), rankings (Tang et al., 2008), and effect analysis, have been undertaken using AMiner (Wang et al., 2010). CiteSeerX is the first academic digital library to provide an independent citation index. CiteSeerX differs from other academic digital libraries and search engines in that all files are gathered from publicly accessible websites. [28] As a result, all searchable files on this site are available to users. It also extracts and indexes graphical items such as figures and tables automatically. People can do research using metadata and text extraction services (Williams et al., 2014a). CiteSeerX, on the other hand, has issues with data collecting and information quality (Wu and Giles). Microsoft Academic Search is an academic search engine that automatically creates a researcher's profile by extracting metadata from public data sources. Researchers

profiles comprise bibliographic data (a list of publications, keywords, co-authors, and so on) as well as bibliometric markers (papers, citations, etc.). They are also divided into categories based on the topic of the articles. Simultaneously, it gives several visualizations, such as publication patterns, co-authorship data, and co-authorship pathways (Osborne et al., 2013). [29] Microsoft Academic Search, on the other hand, has several issues. One of them is the problem of data duplication (Ortega and Aguillo, 2014), which necessitates time-consuming data preparation before use. Furthermore, author disambiguation can be a difficult task to navigate (Pitts et al., 2014). Another issue is that data is updated seldom (once a year). The final issue is that many of these profiles are from distant locations.

Google Scholar is an academic retrieval system that includes basic publishing information (titles, co-authors, year of publication, and so on) as well as indications (citation count, i10-index, index, and so on). Unlike Microsoft Academic Search, its researcher profiles are developed and maintained by researchers, making each researcher's information optional. However, this resulted in information standardization flaws (De Winter et al., 2014). It can also refresh the data regularly. [30] Then, by constructing a web parser application, it may be freely accessed and information retrieved (Bar-Ilan, 2008).

Table 2 Methodology of academic social network analysis using machine learning

Conclusion

We have examined the application of several machine learning algorithms in the analysis of social media in this research, and we have offered a comparative examination of the various methodologies. This paper focuses on the study of machine learning techniques in academic social network analysis, with an emphasis on practical implementations and open research possibilities. The theoretical components of academic social network analysis employing machine learning techniques, as well as the representation, were investigated in this research. Academic social networks are a concept developed specifically in the context of academic big data, which refers to the complex academic network established by academic institutions and their connections. To study the rich structural kinds and related information about academic social networks, there are a variety of scholarly big data processing approaches.

Reference

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